

Ultra-Compact Bimodal Interferometric Plasmonic Sensor Integrated on a Polymeric Photonic Waveguide Platform

K. Fotiadis^{1,*}, D. Spasopoulos¹, E. Chatzianagnostou¹, D. Bellas², O. Bhalerao³, St. Suckow³, E. Lidorikis², N. Pleros¹

¹Department of Informatics - Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, 45110, Greece

³AMO GmbH, Advanced Microelectronic Center Aachen (AMICA), Otto-Blumenthal-Strasse, Aachen, Germany

*E-mail: kfotiadi@cspd.auth.gr

Abstract: We demonstrate an ultra-compact bimodal interferometric plasmonic refractive index sensor co-integrated for the first time on a SU-8 photonic waveguide platform. After optimization process the proposed sensor exhibited an experimental sensitivity of 4464 nm/RIU.

OCIS codes: Plasmonic sensors; Surface plasmons; Photonic integrated circuits; Aluminum; Refractive index

1. Introduction

Plasmonic sensors have attracted the interest of the research community due to their high sensitivity credentials stemming from the profound exposure of the supported surface plasmon polariton (SPP) modes to the ambient environment that lead to increase light-matter interaction. However, most plasmonic sensors require bulky prism-based coupling configurations [1] which in combination with their inherent high propagation losses [2] restrict their deployment in practical and multifunctional sensor layouts. To overcome the above problems, a promising solution is the co-integration of plasmonic structures with low-loss photonic waveguide platforms [3]. Towards this direction, we demonstrate a compact, low-cost and ultra-sensitive device based on a single-arm bimodal interferometric plasmophotonic sensor [4]. The proposed device takes advantage of utilizing the CMOS compatible plasmonic metal aluminum and the polymeric material SU-8 for the photonic waveguide platform reducing the overall cost of the fabrication process and enabling quicker turn-around times. After a thorough numerical investigation, the proposed sensor was fabricated and experimentally characterized revealing a bulk refractive index (RI) sensitivity value equal to 4464 nm/RIU, which is in very good agreement with the value of 5605 nm/RIU that was expected from simulations.

2. Sensor Layout and Fabrication

Fig. 1(a) depicts the 3D schematic of the proposed bimodal plasmophotonic sensor. It consists of two access photonic SU-8 waveguides (WG) with dimensions $1.8 \mu\text{m} \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ separated by an $80 \text{ nm} \times 7 \mu\text{m}$ aluminum (Al) metal stripe WG located on top of an appropriately thinner SU-8 WG layer (bottom layer). At the plasmonic area, two metal-insulator interfaces are formed at the top and bottom surfaces of the plasmonic stripe, which are able to support SPP modes of TM polarization. The electric field distribution of the two supported plasmonic modes (named as ‘top’ and ‘bottom’ mode, respectively) is depicted in Fig. 1(c) and (d). Upon excitation through a TM photonic mode propagating in the input SU-8 WG, the two plasmonic modes can propagate along the metal surfaces and interfere at the output SU-8 WG realizing a single arm bimodal interferometer. The top mode is guided at the interface between the metal and the surrounding medium and gets exposed to the overlying aqueous analyte, forming in this way the sensing arm. The bottom mode is guided at the interface between the plasmonic WG and the underlying SU-8 layer, providing the reference signal. A RI change of the liquid sample induces a phase change on the highly-sensitive SPP mode at the top surface of the stripe leading to a wavelength shift at the interferometer

Fig. 1 : (a) 3D schematic of the proposed bimodal sensor, (b) cross-section geometry of the Aluminum plasmonic WG, (c) and (d) the two supported plasmonic modes at the top and bottom metal surfaces, respectively, (e) SEM top-view image of the plasmonic WGs of the fabricated chip, (f) photo from the fabricated chip with a droplet above the plasmonic structure.

Fig. 2 : (a) Measured spectral response for a 100- μm long plasmonic bimodal sensor in air and water conditions, (b) Spectral response of the same sensor when injecting four different liquids with refractive index varying from 1.3320 to 1.3377 yielding a sensitivity equal to 4464 nm/RIU, (c) Equivalent simulation results yielding a sensitivity equal to 5605 nm/RIU and (d) Resonance shift with respect to the above refractive index changes along with the corresponding linear fits for both simulated and experimental measurements.

output. A systematic numerical design analysis took place targeting maximum bulk RI sensitivity and maximum extinction ratio (ER) at the sensor output as well as minimum overall losses. This was achieved by optimising the thickness of the SU-8 layer ($h_{\text{SU8,2}}$) under the aluminum stripe in combination with the appropriate plasmonic stripe length, aiming at optimal interference conditions between the two plasmonic modes at the interferometer output. After determining the optimum dimensions, the proposed bimodal sensor was fabricated and experimentally characterized. A standard 6'' silicon wafer with 3 μm SiO_2 was employed as substrate. The bottom SU-8 layer was then spin-coated on the entire wafer followed by a two-stage soft-bake process on hot-plates, yielding a uniformity of 0.9 μm . Marker layer and waveguides were defined by optical projection lithography using an i-line stepper tool. Then, an 80 nm thick aluminum layer was deposited using a sputter deposition process and was patterned using i-line lithography and wet-etching forming Al plasmonic stripes of varying lengths atop the bottom SU-8 layer. Afterwards, the second SU-8 layer was formed following a similar process with the bottom layer. The final step of the fabrication process was the dicing of the wafer into 2 cm \times 2 cm dies. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of three fabricated bimodal plasmonic interferometers are given in Fig. 1(e).

3. Experimental Results

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed bimodal sensor, broadband fiber to fiber measurements were carried out. For this purpose, the experimental setup consisted of a tunable laser source emitting light from 1500 nm to 1630 nm, a lensed polarization maintaining fiber at the sensor input to ensure that TM light is injected in the chip, a single mode fiber at the chip output and an optical power meter. The first step of the characterization process was the evaluation of the sensor when exposed to air and water conditions, the latter being achieved by injecting a droplet of water on top of the chip, as depicted in Fig. 1(f). The obtained spectral responses of a sensor with a 100 μm -long plasmonic stripe are depicted in Fig. 2(a). The measured free spectral ranges (FSR) are in very good agreement with the expected values from theory (see Fig. 2(a)) and, specifically, were found equal to 42.9 nm and \sim 92 nm when the sensor was exposed in air and water, respectively, showing clearly that the sensor responds as expected when transition from air to aqueous environment occurs. Afterwards, the device sensing capability was evaluated by injecting four different liquids above the plasmonic structure with RI values varying from 1.332 to 1.3377, having being measured by a commercial refractometer. The sensing area was rinsed with deionized water in order to remove any residues between measurements with different analytes. Fig. 2(b) depicts the measured sensor spectral response for the four different liquids revealing the blue shifting of the wavelength dip with increasing RI value of the sample. A fast Fourier transform fitting was applied to the data of each spectrum to better follow the evolution of the sensor dip. Fig. 2(c) shows the corresponding simulation results obtained from circuit level simulations of the complete sensor using the Lumerical "INTERCONNECT" photonic integrated circuit simulator. Bulk RI sensitivity was determined by performing least squares linear fit on the wavelength shifts with the RI change. The experimentally measured sensitivity was found equal to 4464 nm/RIU, which is in very good agreement with the corresponding value of 5605 nm/RIU obtained from the simulation results, as can be seen in Fig. 2(d).

4. Conclusion

We demonstrate a single-arm bimodal interferometric sensor based on a 100- μm long aluminum metal stripe co-integrated for the first time with an SU-8 photonic platform revealing a bulk sensitivity of 4464 nm/RIU.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European H2020 ICT GRACED (no. 101007448) project.

References

- [1] J. Homola et al., Chem. Rev. **108**(2), 462–493 (2008).
- [2] A. Khan, Appl. Phys. Lett. **103**(11), 111108 (2013).
- [3] E. Chatzianagnostou et al., ACS Photonics **6**(7), 1664–1673 (2019).
- [4] E. Chatzianagnostou et al., SPIE conf., 10921, 1664–1673 (2019).